

One-electron stoichiometry is observed in the direct titrations of glutathione, thioglycolic acid and 2-mercaptoethanol, while a two-electron stoichiometry is seen in case of ascorbic acid, sodium arsenite and hydroquinone. A four-electron stoichiometry is noted for hydrazine sulfate.

In case of glutathione, thioglycolic acid and 2-mercaptoethanol, the presence of disulfide in the reaction mixture was detected by paper chromatography, with phenol saturated with water as solvent and ninhydrin as spray reagent⁸. Paper chromatography technique was used to identify the *p*-toluenesulfonamide in the reaction products⁹.

Since the addition of KI is a pre-requisite, that means iodine is formed *in situ* as an essential intermediate,

The thiol is then oxidized by the iodine, in a series of reaction steps,

In case of sodium arsenite, hydrazine sulfate, hydroquinone and ascorbic acid, addition of RNBrAg liberates iodine from KI solution, and the liberated iodine oxidizes the above reductants.

The amount of acid (H_2SO_4) added, determines the degree of oxidation. In case of ascorbic acid, at lower sulfuric acid concentration (<0.3 *N*) the rate of oxidation becomes slower, however, at higher acid concentrations (0.3–1.0 *N*), smooth oxidation takes place. Similarly, sluggish end-points are noticed if the required overall concentration of H_2SO_4 is not used with glutathione, thioglycolic acid and 2-mercaptoethanol. In the oxidation of TGA and MCE, concentration of added KI plays a dominant role.

Determination of ascorbic acid in pharmaceutical preparations : The proposed method has been employed for the determination of ascorbic acid in pharmaceutical preparations. Solutions of the pharmaceutical samples (both tablet and syrup) were prepared so that 10 cm³ of the solution contained 20 mg of ascorbic acid. Estimation was carried out by the recommended procedure by taking 10 cm³ of the tablet or syrup solution. The results are shown in Table 2.

Attempts to carry out a potentiometric titration between the reductant and RNBrAg solution using a platinum electrode were not successful and premature end-points were observed. The formal redox potential of RNBrAg-PTS couple was determined by the extrapolation procedure and found to be +0.862 V at 28° and pH 6.92. The redox potential

Table 2 Determination of ascorbic acid (AA) in pharmaceutical preparations with RNBrAg

Sample	AA Label	Amount of AA found (mg)		
		Recovery \pm SD**		
	claim mg	Proposed method	BAT method	RNCIAG method
Tablet				
Chewcee (Wyeth Lederle) ^d	500	499.3 \pm 0.6	498.9 \pm 0.6	498.8 \pm 0.7
Celín (Glaxo) ^b	500	499.5 \pm 0.5	498.2 \pm 0.5	499.1 \pm 0.6
Limcee (Sarabhai) ^c	100	99.1 \pm 0.6	99.0 \pm 0.6	98.9 \pm 0.6
Redoxon				
(Γ Hoffmann, La Roche) ^d	1000	998.5 \pm 0.5	998.4 \pm 0.5	998.4 \pm 0.6
Oral solution				
Cecon (Abbott Lab) ^e	100	99.2 \pm 0.6	99.0 \pm 0.6	99.5 \pm 0.5

*Batch Nos ^a5318, ^b445, ^cOH 3131, ^dCR 2113, ^eOC 1831

**Average of six determinations

value of RNBrAg is comparable to BAT.

The UV spectrum of RNBrAg is characteristic of benzenoid absorption and can probably be attributed to π - π^* transition. It may be noted that benzenesulfonamide absorbs in this region¹⁰

The UV and IR spectra of RNCIAG and BAT are compared : RNCIAG ; λ_{max} (H_2O) 220 nm, ν_{max} 3069 ($\text{Ar}_{\text{C-H}}$), 1649, 1500, 1455 ($\text{Ar}_{\text{C-C}}$), 1338 (SO_2 -asym), 1162 (SO_2 -sym), 943 (S-N), 564 cm^{-1} (N-Cl); BAT : λ_{max} (H_2O) 224 nm, ν_{max} 3359, 3261 (O-H); 3047 ($\text{Ar}_{\text{C-H}}$), 1599, 1560, 1529 ($\text{Ar}_{\text{C=C}}$), 1304 (SO_2 -asym), 1159 (SO_2 -sym), 906 (S-N), 533 cm^{-1} (N-Br).

Interference studies : Foreign ions (10 mg) such as Ba^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-} , Na^+ and Cl^- did not interfere in the redox titration with RNBrAg. Any oxidizable impurity present even in microlevel interfered in the determination of all the reductants. Common excipients like talc, gum acacia, glucose, lactose, carboxymethylcellulose did not interfere in the determination of ascorbic acid with RNBrAg.

Conclusion : It may be concluded that oxidation with RNBrAg is very similar to BAT and RNCIAG. Also that, a bromamine containing a heavy metal ion is employed for the first time as an oxidimetric reagent.

Experimental

Silver salt of p-toluenesulfobromamide : It was obtained as pale yellow solid (RNBrAg) after mixing equimolar quantities of silver nitrate and bromamine-T solutions, which was washed with dil. NaOH solution and cold water, air-dried and stored in brown bottle. The purity of the com-

pound was checked by UV (JASCO, UVIDEC-610 spectrophotometer) and FT-IR (Nicolet 400D spectrophotometer, KBr) spectra : λ_{\max} (H₂O) 223 nm; ν_{\max} 3050 (Ar_{C-H}), 1628, 1550, 1450 (Ar_{C=C}), 1314 (SO₂⁻-asym), 1164 (SO₂-sym), 947(S-N), 565 cm⁻¹ (N-Br). The compound gave satisfactory Ag, Br, C, H, N and S analyses.

An aqueous solution of RNBrAg (~0.003 N) was prepared in triple-distilled water and standardized by the following procedure. To an aliquot of RNBrAg solution, 2N H₂SO₄ (10 ml) and 20% KI solution (10 ml) were added, shaken well and after ~1 min, the liberated iodine was titrated against standard sodium thiosulfate solution to a starch end-point. The reaction involves a two-electron change as shown in reaction (8).

L-Ascorbic acid (SRL), hydrazine sulfate (s.d.fine), glutathione (s.d.fine), sodium arsenite (Riedel-Hannover), hydroquinone (Sarabhai), thioglycolic acid (s.d.fine) and 2-mercaptoethanol (Loba-chemie) were used as such, and their aqueous stock solutions (0.005–0.02 mol dm⁻³) were prepared.

Procedure : A direct titration between the reductant solution and RNBrAg solution was carried out with a visual end-point. To an aliquot of the reductant solution, 20% KI solution (0.2 ml of 5% KI solution in case of MCE and 0.5–2.0 ml of 5% KI for TGA) was added and titrated slowly with constant stirring against standard RNBrAg solution to the appearance of a pale blue colour. In case of sodium arsenite and hydrazine sulfate, titrations were carried out in a weakly basic medium by adding solid NaHCO₃ (0.5–1.5 g). Titrations of ascorbic acid and glutathione were carried

out by maintaining overall H₂SO₄ concentration of 0.3–1.0 and 0.05–0.80 N, respectively. In case of MCE and TGA, the overall H₂SO₄ concentration was 0.05–1.0 and 0.5–1.0 N, respectively. In case of hydroquinone, titrations were carried out in aqueous medium alone.

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